

was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the concentrated solution was poured into ice cold water. The resulting solid was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to yield the product (3a, 4a ; 0.75 g) which gave a single spot on tlc in benzene - acetone system (Table 1).

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Nitromethane Synthesis with D-Ribose

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FISCHER and Sowden¹ performed experiments in the stepping up of aldoses. Aldoses were condensed with nitromethane in presence of sodium methoxide to form the corresponding nitroalcohols which were then subjected to the Nef reaction² with moderately concentrated sulphuric acid to form the higher aldose.

Here D-ribose has been condensed with nitromethane in presence of sodium methoxide to form 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-altritol (1) and 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-allitol (2). To this mixture some pyridine was then added and the products were separated in a small centrifuge. While 1 dissolved in pyridine, the latter did not. Then 1 was subjected to the Nef reaction

with 7 N H₂SO₄ to form D-altrose (3) and with 2 N H₂SO₄ to form D-allose (4).

Experimental

Condensation of D-ribose with nitromethane: A suspension of D-ribose (2.5 g) in methanol (8 ml) and nitromethane (7 ml) was shaken with a solution of sodium (2.3 g) in methanol (6 ml) and then allowed to stand in an ice-box for 1.5 h when the sodium salts of the sugar nitroalcohols precipitated. The precipitate was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and then with ether. To it pyridine (7.5 ml) was added and the mixture was separated by centrifugation. The epimer 1 dissolved in pyridine while 2 did not. Pyridine was distilled off to obtain 1 (1.8 g), m.p. 68° (Found: C, 34.10; H, 6.09; N, 6.60. Calcd.: C, 34.12; H, 6.11; N, 6.63%); [α]_D -4.2° (H₂O). From the undissolved portion, 2 was obtained (0.2 g), m.p. 46° (Found: C, 34.11; H, 6.10; N, 6.61. Calcd.: C, 34.12; H, 6.11; N, 6.63%); [α]_D +1.2° (H₂O).

Nef reaction of 1 and 2: 1 (1.8 g) was warmed with 7 N H₂SO₄ (4 ml) for 1 h. The excess acid was then removed on an ion-exchange column. From the filtrate D-altrose (3; 1.2 g) crystallised out, m.p. 104°; [α]_D -24° (H₂O); it formed a benzylphenyl-

hydrazone, m.p. 157°. **2** (0.2 g) with 2 N H₂SO₄ (1.4 ml) yielded gelatinous D-allose (**4**; 0.12 g), m.p. 128° [α]_D+7° (H₂O); it formed an osazone, m.p. 173°.

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Chemical Examination of *Buddleia neemda*

B. Ham.

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IN connection with our work on plant pigments¹, phytochemical investigation of *Buddleia neemda* B. Ham. (Syn. *B. asiatica* Lour.; loganiaceae)² has been undertaken. *B. neemda* is a very common shrub occurring throughout India and is used as an indigenous drug in the treatment of skin diseases. Literature survey reveals that the flowers of this plant have been investigated earlier³. We now report the results of chemical examination of the aerial parts (stems and leaves) of this plant on which no work has been done so far.

The air dried powdered aerial parts (stems and leaves) of *B. neemda* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene–chloroform (3 : 1) mixture afforded yellow needles, C₁₇H₁₄O₆ (*M*⁺ 314), m.p. 280°, crystallised from benzene. It gave greenish blue colour with ferric chloride and responded magnesium–hydrochloric acid test for flavonoids. It was found to contain two methoxy groups as indicated by Zeisel experiment and exhibits $\lambda_{\max}$ 255, 310 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200 (br, bonded-OH), 1650, 1605 and 1580 cm⁻¹ (chelated α,β -unsaturated C=O). These spectral data in conjunction with the fact that the compound forms a monomethyl ether, C₁₈H₁₆O₆ (*M*⁺ 328), m.p. 160° on treatment with diazomethane, and a dimethyl ether, C₂₀H₁₈O₆ (*M*⁺ 342), m.p. 188° on reaction with dimethyl sulphate reveals that the compound is a dihydroxydimethoxyflavone. Finally, the flavone was characterised as 5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavone from the comparison of physical properties of this compound and its mono- and dimethyl derivatives respectively with those of the aglycone of 3',4'-dimethylfluteolin-7-O- β -D-glucopyranuronide⁴, 7,3',4'-trimethylfluteolin⁵ and 5,7,3',4'-

tetramethylfluteolin⁶. Incidentally, it appears to be the first report of isolation of this flavone from natural source.

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Chemical Constituents of *Nephrolepis tuberosa*

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IN the course of our investigation on different Indian ferns having insecticidal and biological activity, we undertook the systematic chemical investigation of a hitherto uninvestigated plant, *Nephrolepis tuberosa* (Fam.: *Pteridophytes*), popularly known as *Pani Amla*, which grows abundantly in the Eastern Himalayan region.

The light petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract of the powdered stem and leaves of *N. tuberosa* upon chromatography over silica gel afforded β -sitosterol.

The chloroform extract of the defatted stem and leaves was fractionated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene–chloroform (8 : 2) yielded a compound NT-1 C₃₀H₅₂O₈ (*M*⁺ 444), m.p. 258–60°, [α]_D+20.94°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3360 cm⁻¹ (OH) and 1450, 1380 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl). Absence of any olefinic proton signal and presence of characteristic signals at δ 0.79–1.20 for eight methyl groups coupled with positive L.B. test suggested compound NT-I to be a saturated